

EMERGING ECONOMY: DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND BUSINESS PERFORMANCE: INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP AMONG SMES IN KUALA LUMPUR, MALAYSIA

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ABSTRACT

Digital Transformation (DT) has become a necessity for Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). SMEs represent 98.5% of all enterprises in Malaysia, with a contribution of around 38.2% of total GDP recorded in 2020. DT is changing the way business is conducted from an economic and business point of view, primarily driven by the development of the Internet of Things (IoT), big data, social media, cloud computing, and mobile technology. Therefore, this study examines the relationship between DT and SMEs' business performance. Using a quantitative research approach, an online questionnaire was developed and distributed. The targeted respondents were from SMEs operating in the Central Region of Malaysia. The finding signifies a moderate and significant correlation between DT and business performance among SMEs in Malaysia. This study will help SME management justify allocating resources required for technological infrastructure and expertise. Policymakers will find it helpful to devise suitable strategies for developing human capital and technical requirements for business development.

Keywords: Digital transformation, business performance, social media, cloud computing, big data analytics

INTRODUCTION

Technology has had a significant effect on our lives. Society can see the impact, and we are discovering ourselves in the ongoing transformation and advancement of technical advancements, particularly information and communication technology (ICT). Education, sports, entertainment, management, healthcare, tourism, economics, and communication are just a few of the businesses that rely on ICT. They are all linked, either because ICT is used as a tool or to solve problems [1]. According to Iqbal et al. [2] the majority of SMEs require timely, valuable, and precise decision-making information. For the vast majority of businesses, data has become a valuable asset. Data, for example, can be utilised to learn more about potential clients and their requirements. Furthermore, as one of the Digital transformation (DT) adoptions, SME firms must actively use data. Data is growing at an unprecedented rate today, posing new difficulties and opportunities for individuals and enterprises.

SMEs, according to Barann et al. [4], are more flexible, faster, and have fewer restrictions and resource constraints than larger organisations. Workforce knowledge gaps frequently prevent these organisations from analysing and implementing digitalization potential. Organizations must

understand how SMEs may successfully use their limited resources to generate digital and data-driven innovation while decreasing the risk of failure. The implementation of DT is challenging, and firms frequently require the support coming from external consultants. SMEs, on the other hand, cannot afford to hire pricey third-party appointments for implemented DTs. Instead, SMEs are searching for government sponsored support units. This support unit is frequently an organisational entity comprised of numerous government-funded academic and non-academic institutions. Despite the fact that they are free, they assist SMEs in increasing their knowledge of the potential of digital innovation through workshops, teaching necessary skills through training, and supporting the implementation of selected innovations in projects.

According to Reis et al. [5,] the number of DT studies increased only after 2014. In 2016, journal articles comprised up to 45 percent of all publications, while conference papers made up 55 percent, demonstrating the importance of conference proceedings in DT. The United States of America (21%), Germany (19%), and the Republic of China (5%) contributed the most publications in DT. Singh [6] used the words of Jeff Bezos, an American entrepreneur who was influential in the development of e-commerce and is best known as the founder and CEO of Amazon. He claims that "There is no other option except digital transformation. Companies who are forward-thinking will carve out new strategic options for themselves; those that do not adapt will fail."

Until now, the study on DT and Malaysian Enterprise has been insufficient. Few studies describe the implications of DT outside the purview of Malaysian SMEs. Previous researchers have concentrated on the definition and strategy, while the underlying technology or technology driving DT in the company has received little attention [7], [8], [9], [10] and [11].

The purpose of this study is to close that knowledge gap. An explanation of the selection of the five DT technologies will be provided later in this study. Therefore, the following research questions have been implied:

1. Is there a significant relationship between DT technology (mobile technology) to SMEs business performance in Malaysia?
2. Is there a significant relationship between DT technology (social media) to SMEs business performance in Malaysia?
3. Is there a significant relationship between DT technology (cloud computing) to SMEs business performance in Malaysia?
4. Is there a significant relationship between DT technology (big data analytics) to SMEs business performance in Malaysia?
5. Is there a significant relationship between DT technology (the Internet of Things) to SMEs business performance in Malaysia?

This research aims to enrich the literature on both the digital transformation and business performance concepts by addressing the identified gap and achieving the following research objectives:

1. To investigate the relationship between DT technology (mobile technology) and the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia
2. To investigate the relationship between DT technology (social media) and the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia
3. To investigate the relationship between DT technology (cloud computing) and the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia

4. To investigate the relationship between DT technology (big data analytics) and the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia
5. To investigate the relationship between DT technology (the Internet of Things) and the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia

Over 900,000 SMEs comprising of 98.5 percent of all enterprises in Malaysia. However, due to time constraints, the scope of this investigation must be narrowed. As a result, the target population is limited to the centre region. According to statistics provided from the iks.my portal for SME Directory, there are 415 SMEs registered in the central region. The centre region was chosen because the central region's neighbouring urban regions are Malaysia's most developed and economically fastest-growing region. Malaysia's commercial insurance, real estate, media, and arts centres are located in the central region, most likely in Kuala Lumpur. Other important economic activity in the region includes education and health care.

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION (DT)

Digital transformation progresses through a series of analog-to-digital transitions, ending in a full-scale evaluation of policy proposals, the working process, and the study of requirements, culminating in a thorough redesign of existing and new digital services. An economic and business viewpoint, Lucas et al. [12] define DT as significantly changing the conventional way business is conducted by redesigning the operational model, procedures, and relationships. Furthermore, Mazzone [13] defines DT as the self-aware and continual transformation path of a firm, a business model, an idea, a system, or a strategic as well as a proactive technique. The identification of DT is emerging, and it could potentially be related to multiple aspects. Mergel et al. [14] define DT as a comprehensive endeavour to alter essential government systems and procedures beyond conventional digitization efforts.

The success of the DT project depends on meeting consumer needs, developing new ways of delivering services, and expanding the target population. The dynamic capabilities theory proposed by Teece et al. [15] serves as the basis for this study. The theory refers to a company's ability to integrate, develop, and reorganise internal and external capabilities. In this study, the theory is useful for generating concepts such as open innovation, digital business strategies, organisational culture, and transformational leadership. Teece [16] distinguishes three major dimensions of dynamic capabilities. The first dimension is a company's ability to identify and shape opportunities and risks. The second is a company's capacity capitalise on identified opportunities. The third category comprises measures to maintain a competitive edge through the merger, protection, and restructuring of intangible and tangible assets.

According to Dibia et al. [17] IT capability is a lower-order capability; then develop it to create a higher-order capability (agility) that can be combined to stimulate competitive actions, such as activities of DT, with other business resources as shown in Figure 1.

In addition, Verina and Titko [18] construct a conceptual model of DT base on three categories: technologies, processes and management, and people. Their research's analysis reveals that technology is the most frequently discussed aspect of the DT definition, followed by processes, data, and business models as shown in Table 1.

Figure 1: IT Capability, Dibia et al. [17]

Table 1: Categories and Elements within DT [18]

Technologies	Management / Process	People
Data		
Big Data	Business Models	Customers
Cloud	Operating Model	Employees
Mobile Devices	Operational Processes	Managers
Social Media	Strategies	Executives
Software	Business Activities	Talents
Analytics	Organizational Culture	Owners
Embedded Devices	Coordination Mechanism	Suppliers
Artificial Intelligence	Products	Partners
The Internet of Things	New Services	Stakeholders
Cybersecurity		Competencies
App Marketplaces		

DT is primarily driven by the technological development of the Internet of Things (IoT), analytics and big data, social media, cloud computing, and mobile technology [19]. Various studies have shown that technology adoption has an essential relationship with business performance [20], and a strong relationship with IT implementation is demonstrated by an organization's structure and processes [20]. The organization's design and operation should support the acceptance and implementation of new technologies relating to big data, IoT, and smart factories, which will lead to improved sustainable business performance among SMEs [18],[19] and [20].

MOBILE TECHNOLOGY (MT)

MT is a protocol that allows mobile devices such as cell phones, iPads, iPhones, iPods, laptops, smart pads, and others to connect to the internet and other services. Many companies have embraced and adopted (and enabled) mobile technology to improve internal and external communication performance, enhancing adaptability in information access and process flows [21].

SOCIAL MEDIA (SM)

SM could be incorporated with little or no extra resources for companies connected to the Internet. Because of its affordable prices and minimal operational specifications, SM can even be used by SMEs. As a result, SM usage is increasing exponentially among companies and is swiftly crucial in business management. SM would seem to be an increasingly common option for businesses since it enables interactions to be multi-to-many beyond a private one-to-one interaction. SM functions also include relatively inexpensive solutions for insights, electronic publishing, business intelligence, engagement tracking, and market targeting. Businesses may also use social media as tools to advertise goods, services, and brands [22].

BIG DATA ANALYTIC (BDA)

BDA can be described by the term 3V, the immense *volume* of information, the vast range of data, and the transmission *velocity*. From multinational corporations to SMEs, business companies worldwide seek ways to use this data to expand their businesses. The use of Big Data is vital in bringing about a significant shift in the business's growth. Today, most business organizations want reliable and accurate supports in the decision-making process. Big data will help SMEs predict their target markets, consumer needs, and desires [2].

CLOUD COMPUTING (CC)

CC changes the way that organizations deploy information technology (IT) services. CC provides all the features with a significantly reduced upfront cost. It also offers an immediate and straightforward path to computing resources for businesses to manage services handle demands. Gartner projected that the global market for public cloud services would rise by 6.3% to a total of USD257.9 billion in 2020, up from USD242.7 billion in 2019 [23].

THE INTERNET OF THINGS (IOT)

IoT is a modern concept of high-tech lifestyle living. These transitions are due to IoT: smart cities, smart houses, pollution reduction, energy savings, smart transport, intelligent industries. IoT is an invention that puts together various smart systems, protocols, and smart devices and sensors [24].

BUSINESS PERFORMANCE (BP)

BP involves an organization's actual results looking at it rather than just at the operational level [25]. The efficient use of ICTs is reflected in the overall performance level of these companies. Hence, companies need to consider the use of technologies to significantly streamline their procedures and administrative activities within their business strategies, which will be reflected in their efficiency, market orientation, profitability, and organizational climate [26].

This research framework is based on the literature reviewed and the DT model by Verina and Titko [18] as shown in Figure 2. Therefore, in this research, the selection of independent variables consists of five variables: mobile devices, social media, analytics, and big data, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things (IoT). The dependent variable is business performance, which measured not specifically both financial performance and non-financial performance but rather than just at the operational level.

Figure 2: Research Framework

The development of the hypothesis refers to the establishment of a logical relationship between the variables. The statement of hypothesis details is as follows.

- H1: Mobile technology is positively related to the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia.
- H2: social media is positively related to the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia.
- H3: Big data analytics is positively related to the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia.
- H4: Cloud computing is positively related to the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia.
- H5: The Internet of things is positively related to the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia.

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology and design suggested the cumulative phase of the distribution of research, including technique and collection of data that have been used. The entire research approaches and structure for this research method are indicated from problem formulation to outcome valuation and all parameters involved [27].

This research uses a quantitative approach since there is an assumed correlation between independent variables and SMEs in Malaysia's business performance. Five independence variables were mentioned in the previous section: mobile technology, cloud computing, social media, big data analytics, and the internet of things. The research approach aims to determine the correlation or relationship between one thing to another or between variables in a population. Therefore, this research focuses on the independent variables of critical technologies for DT and the dependent variable of SMEs' business performance in Malaysia.

Five-point Likert scale were used in the analysis. The scale will help assess the importance of the DT factors affecting SMEs' business performance. In this five-point Likert scale, an ordinal scale of 1 to 5 is being used because it enables the researcher to weigh the importance of the factors that can affect the business performance according to the business owners' perceptions. Hence, the researcher can decide which factors are more critical and which are less critical. A Likert scale proposes a linear ordinal scale within the strength or intensity of an attitude in a particular spectrum, from "Strongly Agree" (value of "5") to "Strongly Disagree" (value "1") and assumptions that opinions can be evaluated [28]. The questionnaire was constructed in two languages, English and Malay. Both were separated within a different form and constructed using MS Forms. The use of bilingualism in the questionnaire produced is to enable the questionnaire to be widely

disseminated and the expectation that there is a different level of language proficiency among entrepreneurs in small and medium enterprises operating in Malaysia. There are eight sections in this questionnaire. It will start with knowledge of DT, demographic information, followed by five key DT technologies: mobile technology, social media, big data analytics, cloud computing, and the internet of things. The last section contains the measure of business performance.

All data were collected using an e-mail-based survey methodology to ensure its objectivity. All emails are composed by inserting a link that leads the recipient to the questionnaire that has been generated. The data collection process was started in October 2020 and ended in early December 2020. Malaysia SMEs information gathered from iks.my portal (<https://iks.my/sme-directory/>).

The guiding principle developed by Krejcie and Morgan [29] was adopted to determine the sample size in this research. As mentioned above, the focus in this research is only for SMEs located in the Central region of Klang Valley and only from the Services sector. Based on the portal, the number of SMEs listed is 415. According to Krejcie and Morgan [29] table for determining sample size based on a given population, therefore for population size 415 ($n = 415$) the determined sample size is 201.

This research chooses simple random sampling as it is easier to understand, have projectable results [30], ease of assembling, unbiased random selection [31], and each member of the population has an equal chance for selection [27].

The collected responses were formatted into analysable data and analysed using Microsoft Excel 365 and SPSS version 26. The first and second sections of the questionnaire were represented using multiple-choice questions and analysed using descriptive analysis and statistical data to research every variable's pattern and frequency. Questionnaires in sections three to eight were represented in the five-point Likert scale, measuring keys technologies in DT.

Cronbach's coefficient alpha was used in this analysis to measure the internal coefficients of the accuracy of the objects used in the questionnaire. Reliability analysis measured the consistency between multiple variables. Internal consistency is commonly used when measuring reliability. The intended analysis is that indicators or scale elements must be highly interrelated and measured in the same construct. Results of the analysis indicate; all six variables have high reliability with the lowest value is 0.840 and the highest value is 0.966. The acceptable range is from 0.7, and the closer the value to 1.0 means higher reliability of the variables. Therefore, to conclude, all variables are within the acceptable range and have high reliability according to the value of alpha in the analysis above.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The male gender dominated the gender demographic characteristic with a total of 127 which is 65.5% of the respondent. The number of females responded to the online questionnaire distributed is at 67 which is 34.5% from all respondents. Regarding the age group, most of the respondents belonged to the 41-50 age group which is 37.6% with a total number of 73 respondents. The second-largest age group is the respondents from the 31-40 age group, with the number of respondents at 57 and 29% from the overall respondents. The smallest age group is below the 20-age group, with only three respondents come from that age group, with only 1.5% of overall respondents. Analysing respondent's roles or levels in their organization, the highest role or level of

respondents is from the managerial level, with a total number of 74 which is 38.1% of overall respondents. The second highest is founder or owner of the business role or level, with the number of respondents at 64 which is 33.0% from overall respondents. The number followed by the executive and representative role or level, with the number and percentage of 38 (19.6%) and 18 (9.3%) respectively. Finally, demographic information of business tenure, majority of the business have been operated more than 15 years, with the number of respondents at 54 which is 27.8% from the overall respondents. The second highest group of respondents come from business tenure lower than 3 years, with the number of respondents at 51 which is 26.3% from overall respondents. The number and percentage followed by business tenure group of 3 to 5 years and 6 to 10 years at 34 (17.5%) and 28 (14.4%) respectively. Finally, the smallest group is from business tenure operated 11 to 15 years with the number at 27 which is 13.9% from overall respondents.

NORMALITY ASSESSMENT

It is a well-known challenge to get perfectly normal distributed data due to sampling limitations. Data is accepted as normally distributed if the value falls between -2 and +2 for both skewness and kurtosis [32]. Moreover, according to Hair et al. [33], skewness values fall outside the -1 to +1 range, indicating a significantly skewed distribution of the data.

Table 2: Normality Test using Skewness and Kurtosis.

		MT	SM	BDA	CC	IoT	BP
N	Valid	194	194	194	194	194	194
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean Statistic		4.2887	4.0954	3.9742	4.0010	3.9774	3.7165
Std. Dev Statistic		0.6268	0.7668	0.7379	0.7587	0.7927	0.6924
Skewness		-0.915	-0.978	-0.944	-1.010	-0.891	-0.320
SE Skewness		0.175	0.175	0.175	0.175	0.175	0.175
Kurtosis		1.803	1.822	1.994	1.732	1.466	0.484
SE Kurtosis		0.347	0.347	0.347	0.347	0.347	0.347

Std. Dev = Standard Deviation; SE = Standard Error

It can be noticed that the skewness and kurtosis for all variables are between the range of -2 and +2, therefore data collected in this research can be concluded as normally distributed.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The correlation between variables can be assessed by applying Pearson's correlation analysis. Correlations are labelled by the lowercase letter *r*, and the value range from +1 to -1. The magnitude of the association between two variables is indicated by the correlation (*r*). This research uses Pearson correlation instead of Spearman correlation due to normally distributed data as has been proven in the above section. This is in line with the explanation by Schober et al. [34] which describes that the Pearson correlation coefficient is typically used for jointly normally distributed data.

Table 3: Pearson Correlation Matrix – Inter Correlations between Variables

		MT	SM	BDA	CC	IoT	BP
MT	PC	1.000					
	S2t						
SM	PC	0.638	1.000				
	S2t	0.000					
BDA	PC	0.451	0.627	1.000			
	S2t	0.000	0.000				
CC	PC	0.473	0.568	0.560	1.000		
	S2t	0.000	0.000	0.000			
IoT	PC	0.38	0.490	0.654	0.615	1.000	
	S2t	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
BP	PC	0.318	0.363	0.457	0.483	0.436	1.000
	S2t	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	

PC - Pearson Correlation; S2t = Sig. (2-tailed)

To describes each association between variables, the hypothesis developed in the previous section will be referred.

- H1: Mobile technology is positively related to the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia. Results from Table 3 indicates, there is a weak correlation or small relationship ($\rho = 0.318$) between mobile technology and business performance. Also, at the 0.01 level, the relationship is significant.
- H2: social media is positively related to the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia. Results from Table 3 indicates, there is also a weak correlation or small relationship ($\rho = 0.363$) between social media and business performance. However, the relationship is also significant at the level of 0.01.
- H3: Big data analytics is positively related to the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia. Between these two variables, results in Table 3 shows, big data analytics, and business performance have a positive moderate correlation ($\rho = 0.457$) or substantial relationship. At the 0.01 level, the relationship is also significant.
- H4: Cloud computing is positively related to the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia. Another variable that has a positive moderate correlation ($\rho = 0.483$) or substantial relationship is between cloud computing and business performance. A significant level of 0.01 also achieves for these variables.
- H5: The Internet of things is positively related to the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia. For the final independent variable, the internet of things, the variable also has a positive moderate correlation ($\rho = 0.436$) or a substantial relationship to business performance. Same as the previous four variables, the internet of things also has a significant relationship level at 0.01.

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Multiple linear regression is chosen because there are five independent variables consist of mobile technology, social media, cloud computing, big data analytics, and the Internet of Things. Result from analysis using SPSS show the significance of the effect from each variable to the dependent variable.

Table 4: Coefficients – Significance of Effect

Model		Unstandardized Coef.		Standardized Coef.	t	Sig.	Coll. Statistics	
		b	SE	Beta			Tolerance	Vif
1	(Constant)	1.278	0.323		3.950	0.000		
	MT	0.068	0.089	0.062	0.765	0.445	0.573	1.744
	SM	-0.023	0.092	-0.023	-0.250	0.803	0.428	2.336
	BDA	0.208	0.090	0.213	2.304	0.022	0.442	2.260
	CC	0.252	0.078	0.277	3.222	0.002	0.511	1.958
	IOT	0.101	0.077	0.115	1.305	0.193	0.482	2.074

Using basic multiple linear regression equation.

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_pX_p$$

Multiple linear regression equation for this model can be constructed as.

$$BP = 1.278 + (0.068*MT) + (-0.023*SM) + (0.208*BDA) + (0.252*CC) + (0.101*IOT)$$

The above model represents the value of a regression equation's function to predict the dependent variable from the independent variable. The following is an explanation of the aforementioned model:

- The intercept, or Y value, is 1.278 when all independent variables are zero.
- If the other independent variable remains constant, company performance will increase by 0.068 units for every unit increase in mobile technology.
- If the other independent variable remains constant, each unit of growth in social media will result in a -0.023 unit rise in business performance.
- If another independent variable remains constant, company performance will grow by 0.208 units for each unit of increment in big data analytics.
- If the other independent variable remains constant, each unit of increase in cloud computing will boost company performance by 0.252 units.
- If the other independent variable remains constant, business performance will grow by 0.101 units for each unit of increment on the Internet of Things.

CONCLUSION

Digital transformation (DT) is a competitive action done by an organization derived from its ability to assemble, integrate, and deploy IT resources. Five technologies were chosen for these studies, mobile technology, social media, big data analytics, cloud computing, and the Internet of Things. Using data-driven insights to understand customers and feeds into business strategy enables hyper-personalization, relevancy, real-time feedback, and agility. Merely having the technology in place is not enough. If a business succeeds in the future, the organization must adopt and apply a company culture that embraces the change.

This research used an integrated model to study DT usage elements among Malaysia's SME organizations. Aspects of DT, such as artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and app marketplaces,

are not considered for this research. This research can be generalized by replicating it in other developing countries.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection and analysis and writing and revising the manuscript.

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